

MASS MEDIA AS A POWERFUL TOOL OF PROPAGANDA

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Abstract: this article explains that the mass media as a powerful propaganda tool is important in society and in the lives of young people.

Key words: globalization, Internet, idea, development, book, consciousness, problem.

Introduction:

The mass media, the Internet, including social networks and mobile messengers, should carry out continuous monitoring of information that has a negative impact on the opinion of the general population, and the information services of relevant state bodies and organizations should be sent to them for a response. The logic of changes and reforms requires everyone to work in a new way, to come up with new ideas and initiatives. In this sense, we are working hard to strengthen the material and technical base of mass media, to strengthen the capacity of personnel, to achieve a worthy place for our national press in the international arena, to develop internet journalism, to introduce market mechanisms in publishing, book trade, and subscription issues, to establish work in an environment of openness and healthy competition. In today's process of globalization, the socio-economic development of humanity has changed radically. As a result of these changes, a number of urgent and significant problems have arisen, the sphere of influence of which covers the world community, and which determine the future social development of mankind. These problems are called global problems of humanity, and it is desirable to concentrate the efforts of all countries in order to find their solution.

Of the global problems, the problem of maintaining peace and disarmament is the most universally important, because if this problem is not solved, the future of life and civilization on Earth will inevitably be in a very sad state. In the history of mankind, according to some data, there have been more than 14,000 wars, and unfortunately, military conflicts and conflicts are still taking place in different regions of our planet. However, at the global level, this problem intensified in the 20th century, when two world wars took place with a total of more than 70 million casualties.¹ Currently, the United States, the Russian Federation, Great Britain, France, China, India and Pakistan are officially recognized by the world community.

War and military conflicts are taking place in different regions of the world. Due to military operations and civil wars, some countries have reached a situation of humanitarian disaster. Examples of this include Syria, Iraq, Libya, Somalia, Afghanistan, South Sudan and other countries.

As a result of rapid changes in the information society, "the acceleration of the process of globalization in the 20th century and the beginning of the formation of a global civilization changed the character of world ideologies. The lack of a powerful ideology to replace them, and the change in geopolitical goals, have strengthened the negative impact of these ideas. In such conditions, only a nation that has clearly defined its goal, has a good understanding of its needs and interests, has its own beliefs, and in a word, has formed its own national idea, will preserve its future and determine its prospects. The Uzbek people, formed as such a nation, on the basis of their centuries-old national idea, enrich the worldview of young people with advanced technologies, realize their identity based on various influences, respect national values and carry aesthetic culture into the future is always ready to deliver.

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